

Version 3.0 - laserbeamFoam: Laser Ray-Tracing and Thermally Induced State Transition Simulation Toolkit

Tom. Flint^{a,*}, Petar. Čosić^b, Gowthaman. Parivendhan^b, Simon. A. Rodriguez^b, Ivan. Bunaziv^c, Patrick. O’Toole^d, Philip. Cardiff^{b,*},

^a*Henry Royce Institute, Department of Materials, University of Manchester, UK*

^b*I-Form Centre for Advanced Manufacturing, School of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, University College Dublin, Ireland*

^c*Materials and Nanotechnology, SINTEF Industry, Torgarden, NO-7465 Trondheim, Norway*

^d*Institut für Strahlwerkzeuge (IFSW), Universität Stuttgart, Pfaffenwaldring 43, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany*

Abstract

This update to the growing laserbeamFoam toolbox introduces significant enhancements to the open-source simulation framework for laser-material interaction, enabling high-fidelity modeling of complex multiphysics phenomena. In this release, we extend the toolbox’s capabilities to support fully compressible, multi-component, and multi-state flow through the **compressibleLaserbeamFoam** solver. Additionally, the original **laserbeamFoam** solver now has the option to use the isoAdvector interface treatment. This update also introduces tools to improve the coupling between all solvers in the toolbox and the discrete element method (DEM) that are used to generate particle placements using Lagrangian methods (namely, coupling with the open-source **LIGGGHTS** software). Another significant enhancement to the simulation toolbox is an overhaul of the laser discretisation and ray-tracing algorithm, decoupling the laser spatial resolution from the mesh resolution and improving the ray-tracing algorithm’s parallel performance.

Keywords: thermal-fluid-dynamics , multi-component , laser-deposition, compressible, additive-manufacturing, laser welding

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: Tom.Flint@manchester.ac.uk (Tom. Flint), philip.cardiff@ucd.ie (Philip. Cardiff)

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Metadata

<u>Nr.</u>	<u>Code metadata description</u>	<u>Please fill in this column</u>
C1	Current code version	V3.0
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/laserbeamFoam/LaserbeamFoam
C3	Code Ocean compute capsule	No
C4	Legal Code License	GNU GPL V3
C5	Code versioning system used	git
C6	Software code languages, tools, and services used	C++, C, MPI
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	OpenFOAM-2506
C8	If available Link to developer documentation/manual	https://github.com/laserbeamFoam/LaserbeamFoam/README
C9	Support email for questions	tom.flint@manchester.ac.uk philip.cardiff@ucd.ie

1. Description of the software-update

The original **laserbeamFoam** solver, along with the additional **multi-componentlaserbeamFoam** that was released with version 2.0, utilized the phenomenological recoil pressure approach to capture the vapourisation state transition; whereby the material within the domain was treated as incompressible, and a phenomenological ‘recoil pressure’ term was added to the momentum equation [1, 2, 3]. Higher fidelity descriptions of the vapourisation/condensation state transition explicitly capture the volumetric changes associated with these transitions and have typically neglected the additional effects of compressibility within the bulk [4, 5, 6]. Recently Zenz et. al. proposed a mathematical framework that not only captured the volumetric changes due to this vapourisation/condensation state transition, but additionally these bulk compressibility effects where the density is considered a function of the temperature and pressure [7, 8, 9]. These higher fidelity approaches, particularly where the compressibility is accounted

16 for, more robustly describe the momentum contribution due to vapourisa-
17 tion/condensation events that operate to stabilise/destabilise thermo-capillaries
18 (keyholes) generated during high energy density laser-substrate interactions.

19 Additionally, the versions 1 and 2 of the toolbox relied on discretizing the
20 laser on one of the numerical domain boundaries. This led to an inherent
21 coupling between the mesh resolution and the allowed resolution of the laser.
22 In this update this is de-coupled and instead the laser is discretised in radial
23 and polar coordinates on a plane normal to the laser direction vector. This
24 change in the code structure necessitated the creation of a specialized com-
25 pactRay C++ class structure to facilitate this implementation in a concise
26 manner. These changes are visible in the src/ directory of the software. Fur-
27 thermore, the original ray-tracing algorithm tracked the discrete rays through
28 the entire domain sequentially; this led to relatively poor parallel scaling due
29 to frequent, low-data, MPI synching calls. In this update the algorithm is
30 completely overhauled and parallel communication of the discrete rays are
31 now performed in batches across processor boundaries.

32 The original **laserbeamFoam** solver is expanded to allow the use of the
33 iso-advecting interface treatment or MULES interface treatment [10, 11, 2]. In
34 this update to the **laserbeamFoam** suite we introduce the **compressible-**
35 **LaserbeamFoam** solver that extends and generalises the multi-component
36 version (named **multicomponentlaserbeamFoam** in version 2.0) to in-
37 clude both the volumetric changes due to the vapourisation/condensation
38 state transitions of the multi-component substrate as well as general pres-
39 sure and temperature dependent compressibility effects. The **compress-**
40 **ibleLaserbeamFoam** framework treats the domain as comprising of $2N +$
41 1 discrete ‘components’ separated into all the metallic chemical components
42 in their condensed and vapour states ($2N$ where N is the number of independ-
43 ent chemical elements in the domain) and one non-condensing/vapourising
44 background gaseous phase; of course this could be generalized to any num-
45 ber of reacting or non-reacting gas phases in the future. This new solver,
46 along with all solvers now use the generalised **laserHeatsource** object that
47 handles the laser ray-tracing. This **laserHeatsource** object has recieved
48 several key updates and performance improvements; including generalising
49 to M independant laser sources such that now a user can simulate multi-
50 component multi-laser scenarios. Furthermore, this update introduces the
51 tools required for greater coupling between discrete element method tools,
52 namely LIGGGHTS, and the laserbeamfoam solvers through the **setSolid-**
53 **Fraction** utility that can read the output of DEM simulations and generate
54 the input files for a thermal fluid dynamics simulation by one of the laser-
55 beamfoam solvers.

56 The original GitHub repository has expanded to an organisation to facil-

57 itate further developments in the laser-substrate interaction space, including
58 the generation of a website. The dedicated website, www.laserbeamfoam.com,
59 [com](http://www.laserbeamfoam.com), has been constructed to host information related to the project, such
60 as relevant and up-to-date publications along with descriptions and links to
61 the latest solver and utility code bases. The website also contains online
62 tools in the form of web applications aimed at helping users improve their
63 workflow for conducting simulations using the **laserbeamFoam** solver. The
64 new **LPBF Workbench** app [https://laserbeamfoam.com/utilities/](https://laserbeamfoam.com/utilities/LPBFWorkbench/app.html)
65 [LPBFWorkbench/app.html](https://laserbeamfoam.com/utilities/LPBFWorkbench/app.html) allows users to generate input files for the discrete
66 element method simulations of the powder deposition using **LIGGGHTS**
67 open-source software, along with input files for the laser properties and sim-
68 ulation parameters tailored for simulating the LPBF process using **laser-**
69 **beamFoam** [12].

70 1.1. compressibleLaserbeamFoam

71 Mathematically describing multi-component substrates subjected to high
72 energy density sources of heat requires capturing the volumetric changes
73 that occur due to the changing density of the substrate (typically the vapour
74 state of a given metallic element has a significantly lower density than its
75 condensed state) [7, 5, 6]. Another source of volumetric change is the fact
76 that the density of metallic components is in reality a function of temperature
77 and pressure in all states of matter [7, 13, 14, 15].

78 One of the major updates to the **laserbeamFoam** suite of solvers and
79 utilities is the addition of a pressure based multi-component compressible
80 solver that explicitly captures the transitions between liquid and vapour
81 phases for the chemical components within the domain. This new solver
82 conserves mass through the solution of $2N+1$ volume fraction transport equa-
83 tions (N metallic species' condensed and vapour phases, plus non-condensing
84 gas phase); where the metallic components are decomposed into their liq-
85 uid and vapour states and the non-condensing/vapourising gas phase is also
86 mathematically described. Equation 1 shows the mathematical form of the
87 transport equation for the k^{th} component.

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_k \alpha_k)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_k \mathbf{U} \alpha_k) = \nabla \cdot (\epsilon_1 D_{kl} \nabla (\rho_k \alpha_k)) + \dot{m}_{kl}. \quad (1)$$

88 In Equation 1, D_{kl} is the pair-wise diffusion coefficient between compo-
89 nents k and l . The mass transfer rate, \dot{m}_{kl} , captures transition between the
90 condensed state and vapourised state of a given chemical component; nat-
91 urally the mass lost from state of a chemical component (e.g. Fe_{liquid}) is
92 gained by the other state (e.g. Fe_{vapour}) during condensation and vapourisa-
93 tion state transitions. We consider pressure driven state transitions following

94 the work of [7]. The transfer rates between the condensed and vapourised
 95 states for a given condensing/vapourising chemical (metallic in our case)
 96 component are:

$$\dot{m}_{kl} = |\Upsilon| (p_{sat} - p) \quad (2)$$

97 where p_{sat} is the saturation pressure, the pressure at which a vapor com-
 98 ponent is in thermodynamic equilibrium with its condensed state. p_{sat} is
 99 calculated according to the Clausius–Clapeyron law. At pressures greater
 100 than saturation pressure, vapour will condense, while at lower pressures it
 101 will evaporate or sublime.

$$p_{sat} = p_{ref} e^{\frac{M L_{vap}}{T_{vap} R} \left(1 - \frac{T_{vap}}{T}\right)} \quad (3)$$

102 where T_{vap} , L_{vap} , M are the chemical components vapourisation tempera-
 103 ture, heat of vapourisation and molar mass respectively. p_{ref} and R are the
 104 reference pressure and universal gas constant. The constant Υ is obtained
 105 from the Hertz-Knudsen model, related to the theoretical maximum instan-
 106 taneous evaporation rate (or condensation rate, depending on the sign of the
 107 pressure difference).

$$\Upsilon = \begin{cases} \frac{\varepsilon_c}{\xi} \sqrt{\frac{M}{2\pi RT}} & \forall p_{sat} > p, \\ -\frac{\varepsilon_c}{\xi} \sqrt{\frac{M}{2\pi RT}} & \forall p_{sat} < p, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

108 where ξ is the liquid–vapour interface thickness. Numerical diffusion at the
 109 interface, is counteracted through application of an interface compression
 110 term between the gaseous/vapour and condensed phases in a pair-wise fash-
 111 ion in an approach adapted and generalised from the standard 2-phase vol-
 112 ume of fluid approach [16, 17]. Naturally, interface compression should be
 113 applied between the gas/vapour and condensed components and diffusion
 114 be applied between condensed-condensed phase pairs and vapour/gaseous-
 115 vapour/gaseous pairs. The implementation of the diffusion model has been
 116 validated against analytical solutions for binary diffusion. Finally, the con-
 117 servation of energy is written as

$$\frac{\partial(\rho E)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{U} E) + \nabla \cdot (p \mathbf{U}) - \nabla \cdot (\kappa \nabla T) = q_{laser} + q_{fus} + q_{vap} \quad (5)$$

118 where E is the total energy including the kinetic energy contribution, given
 119 as: $E = e(T) + \frac{\mathbf{U}^2}{2}$ with the specific internal energy generally given as
 120 $e(T) = C_v T$ where T is the absolute temperature and C_v is the heat capac-
 121 ity at constant volume (however any available OpenFoam thermodynamic

122 model can be used). κ is the thermal conductivity coefficient of the material.
 123 q_{laser} , q_{fus} and q_{vap} are the energy deposited by the laser, and the latent heat
 124 contributions due to the fusion and vapourisation state transitions respec-
 125 tively. Figure 1 shows the **compressibleLaserbeamFoam** solver applied
 126 to a multi-component metallic substrate. In this example the substrate is
 127 initial comprised of a homogenous mixture of Fe, Ni and Mn, with volume
 128 fractions of 0.5, 0.4 and 0.1 respectively. This substrate is subjected to a
 129 simulated laser irradiation of 1000W, with a laser radius of $40\mu m$. In this
 130 example problem, meant to display the applicability of the new solver, the
 131 laser traverses across the substrate at a speed of $0.5m s^{-1}$.

Figure 1: Simulated initiation of a thermo-capillary generated through laser-irradiation of a multi-component (Fe - Ni - Mn) substrate using the **compressibleLaserbeamFoam** solver. The vapour plume composition is shown for an arbitrary time-step.

132 Figure 1 shows the **compressibleLaserbeamFoam** solver applied to
 133 a multi-component substrate. It can be seen in the figure that the vapour
 134 plume is ejected from the keyhole and undergoes significant volumetric expan-
 135 sion due to the significantly lower density of the vapour state. Additionally

136 the vapour component volume fractions are plotted in the figure, showing
137 that the solver resolves this complex physics. Interestingly the component
138 fractions of the vapour is not equal to the condensed state volume fractions;
139 reflecting the complex governing physics during vapourisation and differences
140 in saturation pressures of the constituent components within the substrates.

141 1.2. Powder bed generation via Discrete Element Method (DEM).

142 The support for initializing powder beds using particle data, generated
143 using the discrete element method through the **LIGGGHTS** open source
144 software **LIGGGHTS** [12], is facilitated using a new dedicated utility **set-**
145 **SolidFraction**. This utility converts particle position data into a volume
146 fraction field in the OpenFoam mesh, enabling the incorporation of DEM-
147 resolved powder beds into simulations using any of the included solvers.

148 The **setSolidFraction** utility allows users to map and initialize spatially
149 heterogeneous powder beds from the output of the DEM simulation to the
150 initial OpenFOAM field. This capability enhances the physical fidelity of
151 simulations involving laser powder bed fusion and other powder-based addi-
152 tive manufacturing processes, particularly where initial powder morphology
153 influences melt behaviour and defect formation. Additionally, the output
154 from an OpenFOAM LPBF simulation can also be used iteratively with the
155 DEM software in order to obtain multi-layer simulations of the laser powder
156 bed fusion process using the **laserbeamFoam** solver.

157 Figure 2 shows the illustration of a typical workflow of the Laser Powder
158 Bed Fusion (L-PBF) simulation using laserbeamFoam.

159 Firstly, a Discrete Element Method (DEM) simulation can be conducted
160 using the LIGGGHTS software by utilizing the input file that can be found
161 in one of the tutorial cases or which can be generated using the mentioned
162 LPBF Workbench app for an arbitrarily sized domain. After that, the set-
163 SolidFraction utility, which utilizes the coordinates and the radius of the
164 particles found in the location file, can be used in order to modify the initial
165 alpha.metal field.

166 Once the alpha.metal field is initialized correctly, the L-PBF simula-
167 tion using laserbeamFoam can be set up and conducted by modifying the
168 timeVsLaserPosition and timeVsLaserPower input files based on the wanted
169 processing parameters. These files can also be generated using the LPBF
170 Workbench app or found in the solver tutorials. Figure 3 a) shows the uti-
171 lization of laserbeamFoam for simulating the L-PBF process while Figure 3
172 b) shows the melted track as the output of the simulation rendered using
173 Blender 4.1.

Figure 2: A powder bed on top of a solid substrate, generated using LIGGGHTS, and fed into the **laserbeamFoam** eco-system using the **setSolidFraction** utility.

(a) Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) simulation using the **laserbeamFoam** solver. The laser is rendered in green and the multiple reflections of the laser with the metallic substrate can be observed.

(b) Rendering of the simulated melt track rendered in Blender 4.1.

Figure 3: Simulation and subsequent rendering of a **laserbeamFoam** simulation of an arbitrary L-PBF process.

174 1.3. Interface treatment using MULES and isoAdvector

175 Versions 1.0 and 2.0 of the project exclusively used the MULES (Mul-
 176 tidimensional Universal Limiter with Explicit Solution) algorithm for deal-
 177 ing with the interface advection within the Volume of Fluid approach. As
 178 shown in [2], the Iso-Advector approach can have advantages in some cases
 179 over MULES due to its sharper interface tracking and reduced numerical
 180 diffusion. Figure 4 shows the comparison in the topology between the two
 181 approaches in an example case simulated using **laserbeamFoam**. In this
 182 update to the codebase there is now the option to use either the MULES
 183 approach or the Iso-advecter approach within the **laserbeamFoam** solver.
 184 This is achieved through a switch in `constant/transportProperties` called
 185 `interfaceTrackingScheme` that the user can use to specify the interface

186 tracking approach. The **compressibleLaserbeamFoam** solver exclusively
 187 uses MULES. As previously mentioned, for posterity, the isoAdvector only
 188 solver **laserMeltFoam** is also included in this release [2]. Figure 4 shows a
 189 comparison between the results obtained from a simulation using isoAdvector
 190 and MULES respectively.

Figure 4: Comparison of simulation results of a L-PBF process using isoAdvector and MULES interface treatments. Three time-steps are shown; in the lower sub-figures the MULES iso-surface is shown in red and the isoAdvector iso-surface in white.

191 As can be seen from Figure 4, both schemes produce similar results.

192 However, due to the very complex nature of the Laser Powder Bed Fusion
193 and Laser Welding processes, where the surface tension effects play a big role
194 in the shape and the evolution of the melt track, the chosen numerical scheme
195 can result in subtle differences in simulated material topology. It is an area
196 of investigation as-to which scheme is better suited to certain scenarios. This
197 addition makes the solvers more flexible and allows the user to choose the
198 approach that better suits the simulation type and conditions of their case.

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